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***Fratelli Tutti*, Technology, and Shannon Vallor's Technomoral Virtues**

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Abstract: In his encyclical letter *Fratelli Tutti* Pope Francis explores a range of topics synthesizing his moral theology and clarifying its relevance for our world and contemporary political realities. In this, he makes a series of pithy observations constituting a robust reflection on the ethical challenges of digital technologies. He cites with insight many of the key benefits of these technologies, such as the promise of great social connection. However, he highlights many well-known problems, especially the reality of greater social alienation and worse,

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dehumanization and other troubling realities. He offers a

pathway to a hopeful future in what amount to a set of spiritual disciplines in the form of his reflections on dialogue, encounter, and kindness. This essay frames the Pope's reflections around a brief look at the philosophy of technomoral virtues developed by the American philosopher Shannon Vallor in her book *Technology and the Virtues*. Vallor's work offers a promising example of careful, detailed, yet appropriately general examination of virtue ethics that is tailored to 21st century technological realities. Her analysis of technomoral virtues offers a bridge to engage Francis's prescient thought in productive dialogue with the emerging and badly needed debate about how national policies can respond appropriately to current challenges. We face an urgent call to address the potent combination of highly useful yet deeply problematic digital technologies and the enormously powerful tech corporations whose unprecedented profits depend upon the ubiquitous proliferation of their products. Together, Vallor's and the Francis's ethical reflections contribute to addressing the moral challenges of harnessing digital technologies for good ends and minimizing their harm.

Keywords: Technomoral Virtues, Shannon Vallor, Technology, Encounter, Dialogue, *Fratelli Tutti*.

Saint Francis “heard the voice of God, he heard the voice of the poor, he heard the voice of the infirm and he heard the voice of nature. He made of them a way of life. My desire is that the seed that Saint Francis planted may grow in the hearts of many”. (Pope Francis, *Fratelli Tutti*, 48)

Introduction

Recently, I was having dinner with old friends. The topic of various technology companies and their business models

came up. One friend who has worked in the industry for quite a while said this when Facebook/Meta came up. He had been courted several times by them. His reaction to these invitations was: “If faced with the choice between taking a job with Facebook/Meta or working to re-elect Donald Trump in 2024 – it would be a close call”. Let’s just say, he’s no fan of the former U.S. president. We laughed. Knowing I would be discussing some of these questions with students soon, the words stuck with me and I followed up with an email a few days later.

Two of the friends replied to my email, including the one with the pithy dilemma. They offered a wealth of reflections and further reading to flesh out the ethically problematic nature of Facebook’s business-model in addition to decisions of its leaders. Much could be said here, but this quotation sums up some of the key problems with Facebook’s style according to a recent analysis (2020) by Adrienne LeFrance of *The Atlantic*:

The cycle of harm perpetuated by Facebook’s scale-at-any-cost business model is plain to see. Scale and engagement are valuable to Facebook because they’re valuable to advertisers. These incentives lead to design choices such as reaction buttons that encourage users to engage easily and often, which in turn encourage users to share ideas that will provoke a strong response. Every time you click a reaction button on Facebook, an algorithm records it, and sharpens its portrait of who you are. The hyper-targeting of users, made possible by reams of their personal data, creates the perfect environment for manipulation—by advertisers, by political campaigns, by emissaries of disinformation, and of course by Facebook itself, which ultimately controls what you see and what you don’t see on the site. Facebook has enlisted a corps of approximately 15,000 moderators, people paid to watch unspeakable things—murder, gang rape, and other

depictions of graphic violence that wind up on the platform. Even as Facebook has insisted that it is a value-neutral vessel for the material its users choose to publish, moderation is a lever the company has tried to pull again and again (LeFrance, 2020).

But there simply aren't enough moderators who speak enough languages to tamp down the deluge of harmful material "because 10 times out of 10, the algorithm is faster and more powerful than a person. At megascale, this algorithmically warped personalized informational environment is extraordinarily difficult to moderate in a meaningful way, and extraordinarily dangerous as a result" (LeFrance, 2020).

The revelation of the so-called Facebook papers, reported first in September 2021, leaked by former Facebook manager Frances Haugen, as well as her calm and illuminating testimony before the US Congress, has only added to the drama. Ishaan Tharoor of *The Washington Post* quotes Le France:

The Facebook Papers 'are astonishing for two reasons,' wrote *the Atlantic's* Adrienne LaFrance. 'First, because their sheer volume is unbelievable. And second, because these documents leave little room for doubt about Facebook's crucial role in advancing the cause of authoritarianism in America and around the world. Authoritarianism predates the rise of Facebook, of course. But Facebook makes it much easier for authoritarians to win' (Tharoor, 2021).

How can religious communities, particularly Catholic communities, helpfully and decisively respond to such challenges? In his recent encyclical letter, *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis reflects extensively upon the challenge of digital technologies. He outlines an array of serious

difficulties for human solidarity linked to the explosion of such technologies in day-to-day life worldwide. This essay frames these reflections around a brief look at the account of *technomoral virtues* developed by the philosopher Shannon Vallor in her book *Technology and the Virtues*. Vallor's work offers a careful, detailed, yet appropriately general examination of virtue ethics carefully tailored to 21st century technological realities. Her analysis offers the kind of bridge needed to bring the Francis's prescient thought into productive dialogue with the emerging, passionate, and much-needed debate about how national policies can respond appropriately to the challenges of the emerging suite of digital technologies. The urgency arises in part because of the usefulness of many of the technologies, which can mask their toxic effects or simply convince many such effects are simply unavoidable collateral damage. Urgency also arises from the enormously wealthy and powerful corporations whose profits depend upon the ubiquitous proliferation of their products. Together Vallor's and Francis's ethical and moral theological frameworks offer a significant contribution to addressing the moral challenges of harnessing digital technologies for good ends and minimizing their harm.

1. *Fratelli Tutti* and the Critique of Digital Technologies

Let us first note two key themes Pope Francis emphasizes throughout the letter: the dignity of each person, and genuine cooperation among people and communities. The former we will explore in section 3 when we discuss his themes of dialogue and encounter. He argues concerning the latter that if communities globally truly work together, and this requires genuine dialogue, genuine encounter, then we can truly build on our dreams. "No one can face life in isolation... We need a community that supports and helps us, in which we can help one another to keep looking ahead. How important it is to dream together... By ourselves, we risk seeing mirages, things that are not there. Dreams, on the other hand, are built together" (FT 8).

Unsurprisingly Francis aims to spur our imagination with hope. But along the way he has some sharp words stating the challenges.

Like so many advances in technology modern digital technologies face the problem of the double-edged sword. The positive promise of digital technologies has been sold for decades. These include technologies such as the internet in general, as well as platforms such as Google, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Surely there is much truth in such optimistic rhetoric as Francis correctly observes. For example, I have been able to communicate with the editor of this publication via email making my contribution possible. A daughter of mine recently helped open a new business and they market their shop largely through their Instagram account. However, Francis shines a light on the damage being done by means of these technologies and the economic structures bound up with them. They are at the forefront of a gold rush. The fortunes already made will make it very difficult to check excess damage from the technologies if those very excesses are necessary conditions for maximizing profits. This threatens to increase wealth gaps within the already wealthy nations (especially where there are not already in place the sorts of policies to check this). It threatens also to increase the gap between wealthier more powerful nations and those still developing.

We are more alone than ever in an increasingly massified world that promotes individual interests and weakens the communitarian dimension of life. Indeed, there are markets where individuals become mere consumers or bystanders. As a rule, the advance of this kind of globalism strengthens the identity of the more powerful, who can protect themselves, but it tends to diminish the identity of the weaker and poorer regions, making them more vulnerable and

dependent. In this way, political life becomes increasingly fragile in the face of transnational economic powers that operate with the principle of “divide and conquer” (FT 12).

Indeed, those economic powers are significant. The top companies in the world, measured by market capitalization, are now primarily the tech giants – Apple (1), Microsoft (2), Alphabet (Google) (4), Amazon (5), and Facebook (6), with Chinese company Tencent up and coming (11) (Protska, 2021).

Francis offers a litany of ills that he argues are facilitated by digital technologies. By these he seems to mean things such as: modes of access to the internet, laptop computers, smart pad and smart phone technologies, Wi-Fi technology, high speed cable, and of course, the various social media platforms that take advantage of these tools. Among the problems he associates with the proliferation of such technologies, foremost is a flattening of discourse which he will address later in his discussion of dialogue and encounter. Dialogue and encounter provide, he argues, a model of a truly rich engagement of human beings with each other and with Creation as a whole (something he discussed at length in *Laudato Si'*). The technologies afford (i.e. make it tempting and easy) to separate what we say from their human effects (more on this later, but for an example of the ill effects of a loss of dialogue with eye-contact, see, for example, Benton 2017 and Lapidot-Lefler and Barak 2012). He discusses the emergence of broad surveillance and a loss of privacy, but also a sense of deeper social isolation. The technologies too easily allow for us to cut ourselves off from that which makes us uncomfortable. We'll discuss briefly Vallor's commentary on this in terms of allowing people to avoid some necessary social friction, but in ways that can lead to working through hard conversations. The extremes too easily prevail between calling people out “on blast” or simply avoiding any difficult conversation.

Let us look at some of these challenges highlighting Francis's own particular commentary upon each sort. He argues that the

technologies allow for a weakening of people's sense of history and tradition in part by emptying important words and concepts of their meaning. "One effective way to weaken historical consciousness, critical thinking, the struggle for justice and the processes of integration is to empty great words of their meaning or to manipulate them." He observes that words such as "democracy, freedom, justice or unity" are being emptied of meaning because co-opted by the powerful (FT 14).

Related to these developments are an unending stream of toxic exchanges and never-ending election cycles that are increasingly partisan (surely true from my vantage point in US politics but it seems to be a problem elsewhere too; I'll leave it to the reader to assess this claim in light of their local political landscape(s)). Many comment sections of online editions of new outlets have been taken down because of a flood of hyperbolic scorn and otherwise harmful content. He observes that we have come to see "ridicule, suspicion, and relentless criticism – marketing techniques primarily aimed at discrediting others. . . In this craven exchange of charges and counter-charges, debate degenerates into a permanent state of disagreement and confrontation" (FT 15). Contrary to the repeated slogans of greater connectivity, he notes we are "growing ever more distant from each other" (FT 16).

Surely the set of developments we call the digital age did not invent the exploitation of people by other people and surely my own nation, the United States is and will be struggling for a long time with the legacy of such inhuman exploitation from slavery to the genocidal destruction of indigenous cultures. Nevertheless, digital technologies allow for new powers of exploitation and a flattening of discourse and engagement that makes it more likely to see others as less than fully human. At least, this has been seen and remains a serious concern. Francis argues this flattened discourse leads

to people being “treated as disposable – from racism, othering, to criminal networks that trade in deadly goods or human trafficking” (FT 19). Furthermore, we see that, “a readiness to discard others finds expression in vicious attitudes that we thought long past, such as racism, which retreats underground only to keep reemerging” and “continue to shame us, for they show that our supposed social progress is not as real or definitive as we think” (FT 20). Criminal networks use such modern communication technologies with global reach to lure “young men and women in various parts of the world” (FT 24).

In this lengthy paragraph, Francis powerfully consolidates his assessment of the bitter fruits of the new technologies.

Paradoxically, we have certain ancestral fears that technological development has not succeeded in eliminating; indeed, those fears have been able to hide and spread behind new technologies. Today too, outside the ancient town walls lies the abyss, the territory of the unknown, the wilderness. Whatever comes from there cannot be trusted, for it is unknown, unfamiliar, not part of the village. It is the territory of the ‘barbarian’, from whom we must defend ourselves at all costs. As a result, new walls are erected for self-preservation, the outside world ceases to exist and leaves only “my” world, to the point that others, no longer considered human beings possessed of an inalienable dignity, become only “them”. Once more, we encounter “the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, in order to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people. And those who raise walls will end up as slaves within the very walls they have built. They are left without horizons, for they lack this interchange with others” (FT 27).

Technology is constantly advancing, yet it lacks a common roadmap. Where is this taking us – where do we wish to go? We’re certainly in it together whether we like it or not.

Technology is constantly advancing, yet ‘how wonderful it would be if the growth of scientific and technological innovation could come with more equality and social inclusion. How wonderful would it be, even as we discover faraway planets, to rediscover the needs of the brothers and sisters who orbit around us (FT 31).

Covid offered an opportunity and a window of shared challenge, suffering, and sacrifice. But in many places this sense of common purpose has fragmented badly.

True, a worldwide tragedy like the Covid-19 pandemic momentarily revived the sense that we are a global community, all in the same boat, where one person’s problems are the problems of all. Once more we realized that no one is saved alone; we can only be saved together. As I said in those days, “the storm has exposed our vulnerability and uncovered those false and superfluous certainties around which we constructed our daily schedules, our projects, our habits and priorities... Amid this storm, the façade of those stereotypes with which we camouflaged our egos, always worrying about appearances, has fallen away, revealing once more the ineluctable and blessed awareness that we are part of one another, that we are brothers and sisters of one another” (FT 32).

Francis observes that we surely have felt the paradoxes of loss of privacy and surveillance (bringing peering “eyes” in everywhere) while we also grow other ways more distant. Rather than seeing other humans as humans, digital technologies allow each of us to be a constant source of

marketable data or mere spectacle. “Everything has become a kind of spectacle to be examined and inspected, and people’s lives are now under constant surveillance people’s lives are combed over, laid bare and bandied about, often anonymously. Respect for others disintegrates, and even as we dismiss, ignore or keep others distant, we can shamelessly peer into every detail of their lives” (FT 42). A toxic brew has emerged combining huge profits to be made in the digital realm coupled with modes of communication that allow for de-humanizing and harmful behaviours which include: disinformation, cyber-attacks, and organized ethnic violence. Circles of conversation become too often cul-de-sacs of groupthink stuck with those who think like we do. The term “stickiness” captures the economic motives promoting the most sensational content. The algorithms of many platforms are designed to be as sticky as they can make them.

As he notes, there’s a worry that these technologies allow for runaway and destructive ideological feedback loops and sabotage democratic processes. Political speech is decaying into what’s too often little better than school-yard taunts and bullying (and let’s be honest, owing to mass media that preceded digital technologies, it was not starting from an august perch). And the world-historic fortunes being made via these platforms makes the conflicts of interest hard to rein-in.

Nor should we forget that “there are huge economic interests operating in the digital world, capable of exercising forms of control as subtle as they are invasive, creating mechanisms for the manipulation of consciences and of the democratic process. The way many platforms work often ends up favouring encounter between persons who think alike, shielding them from debate. These closed circuits facilitate the spread of fake news and false information, fomenting prejudice and hate” (FT 45).

Through these media one can avoid encounters with reality; avoid unwanted friction and easily delete those we don't like or who "offend" us.

In the US the notion of cancel culture has become a political tool; but it speaks to something real according to Francis – the use of the tech to cancel, unfriend, block, etc. We think we don't have to deal with the human face of relational tensions. He argues that wisdom requires that we face reality.

Today, however, everything can be created, disguised and altered. A direct encounter even with the fringes of reality can thus prove intolerable. A mechanism of selection then comes into play, whereby I can immediately separate likes from dislikes, what I consider attractive from what I deem distasteful. ... Persons or situations we find unpleasant or disagreeable are simply deleted in today's virtual networks; a virtual circle is then created, isolating us from the real world in which we are living (FT 47).

Furthermore, he describes what many of us have experienced (e.g. class sessions mediated via Zoom): digital relationships lack much of what's crucial for deeper human connectedness. "Digital media can also expose people to the risk of addiction, isolation and a gradual loss of contact with concrete reality, blocking the development of authentic interpersonal relationships'. They lack the physical gestures, facial expressions, moments of silence, body language and even the smells, the trembling of hands, the blushes and perspiration that speak to us and are a part of human communication" (FT 43). And Francis goes on to note that because of this lack of personal connection and other features of the temporal dimension of real-life personal encounters, that such digitally mediated relationships "do not really build community; instead, they tend to disguise and expand the

very individualism that finds expression in xenophobia and in contempt for the vulnerable” (FT 43).¹

As Francis winds down his syllabus of errors he previews the invocation of *dialogue and encounter* as crucial antidotes. He observes that so many of us are losing our ability to have genuine dialogue and conversation. We are impatient, prone to interrupt, if we even bother to engage someone face to face. We can try to engage only what we wish and ignore or block the rest. As noted, there is a whole set of tools helpful for avoiding friction, e.g. difficult conversations, something that we’ll discuss more below in the context of Shannon Vallor’s discussion of virtues. In such avoidance we miss something deeply important.

The ability to sit down and listen to others, typical of interpersonal encounters, is paradigmatic of the welcoming attitude shown by those who . . . accept others, caring for them and welcoming them into their lives. Yet ‘today’s world is largely a deaf world... At times, the frantic pace of the modern world prevents us from listening attentively to what another person is saying. Halfway through, we interrupt him and want to contradict what he has not even finished saying. We must not lose our ability to listen’” (FT 48).

He continues, “A new lifestyle is emerging, where we create only what we want and exclude all that we cannot control or know instantly and superficially. This process, by its intrinsic logic, blocks the kind of serene reflection that could lead us to a shared wisdom” (FT 49). But this leaves us bereft because dialogue, encounter and challenging conversations (friction) are crucial for developing the healthy relationships that allow for love, justice, and peace to obtain.

¹ On this there will be more below. For an example of the downside of a loss of interpersonal contact associated with digital technologies, see Lapidot-Lefler and Barak, 2012.

Francis concludes this section by foreshadowing his main response to the situation – rebuilding the culture of encounter. “Together, we can seek the truth in dialogue, in relaxed conversation or in passionate debate. To do so calls for perseverance; it entails moments of silence and suffering, yet it can patiently embrace the broader experience of individuals and peoples. The flood of information at our fingertips does not make for greater wisdom” (FT 50). The internet may allow for more information at our fingertips than we could have imagined, but it does not make for the wisdom of *what* to seek, *when*, and *how* to apply it. “The process of building fraternity, be it local or universal, can only be undertaken by spirits that are free and open to authentic encounters” (FT 50).

We might wish Francis had more specific proposals for how to respond. His major strategy of reply counsels dialogue, encounter, and kindness. These reiterate what I would call “common sense Christian spiritual disciplines”. However, maybe that’s one crucial proposal among others that’s needed for us to find our way through. It may be good that he does not pretend to have the detailed policy proposals in hand. He is framing a spirituality and moral theology that can guide the pursuit of more particular practices and policies. Someone like Shannon Vallor can help mediate this situation by offering a cross-cultural philosophical reflection on the ethics of technology and relevant virtues. Together, they may help frame the sort of character needed for those who will undertake the further work of shaping an implementing the policies needed.

2. Vallor, Technology, and the Virtues

Shannon Vallor, Professor of Philosophy at the University of Edinburgh and of the Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI), has published a thorough, clear, and compelling account of virtue ethics tailored to the 21st century era of rapid technological

development. *Technology and the Virtues: A philosophical guide to a future worth wanting*, makes the case for virtue-theoretic account of an ethics for technology. She thus discusses character formation in a global context. She explores in detail not just Aristotle's account and its Greek roots, but also Confucian as well as Buddhist versions of virtue ethics. Discussing the three traditions repeatedly in parallel constitutes her case that relevant "technomoral virtues", needed for discerning choices about technology relevant to a future worth wanting, must come to exist in a global context. Francis agrees. Here I will leave the three parallel traditions, as laid out by Vallor, noted rather than explored.

Vallor describes the ailment that we suffer globally as a widening gap between technological power and technomoral wisdom. Near the end of her book she states this need for a cure quite forcefully,

Throughout the book . . . I have suggested the only plausible first step toward a cure: to convene new institutions, communities, and cultural alliances in the service of global technomoral cultivation. This will require intense, cooperative, and sustained human efforts, many of them on a worldwide scale (Vallor, 2016: 249).

And the stakes are high. She repeatedly invokes both our very survival and maybe more plausibly our capacity to live well as a common community. She joins Francis consistently to invoke the common good. Given their shared beliefs that each and every person on earth counts as a member of the relevant community, this is clearly a global task.

One of her main reasons to adopt a virtue ethics approach in response to the technological explosion in the late 20th and early 21st centuries centres on the idea of severe *technosocial opacity*. This concerns the profound difficulty of projecting the expected consequences, good or ill, of the various technological developments and the responses of people to them. Thus, we find

ourselves in a situation where, “on the timescale of our own lives, this environment is increasingly unstable and unpredictable, and it is not clear how much of our accumulated wisdom still applies” (Vallor, 2016: 8). Part of her critique of Kantian ethics, especially the relevance of the categorical imperative, and versions of Millian consequentialism, springs from the inability to calculate the relevant rules. For example, she argues that choices about using biological enhancement technologies, genetic or other, face these problems in light of trying to satisfy any application of Kant’s categorical imperative:

To will a world where all humans enhance their own bodies with technology, won’t you first need to know which parts of ourselves we would enhance, in what ways, and what those changes would do to us in the long run, for example, whether we would end up improving or degrading our own ability to reason morally? (Vallor, 2016: 7).

And the would-be utilitarian faces similar challenges in calculating which course of technological actions promises the greatest happiness for all those affected:

The problem of discerning *which* course of action promises the greatest overall happiness or the least harm—among all the novel paths of biomedical, mechanical, and computational development open to us—is simply incalculable. The technological potentials are too opaque, and too many, to assign reliable probabilities of specific outcomes. Moreover, technology often involves effects on humanity created by the aggregate choices of *many* groups and individuals. When we factor in the interaction effects between converging technologies, social

practices, and institutions, the difficulty becomes intractable (Vallor, 2016: 7-8).

The challenge for virtue ethics will be how to frame some of the virtues, especially *phronesis* (practical wisdom), or what Vallor calls prudential judgment, given such acute technosocial opacity. We may be in a perpetual state of trying not to let the perfect be the enemy of the good—especially if the tools of technology keep promising optimization but can't tell us what we should be optimizing *for*.

The heart of the book lays out what she calls the 7 core elements of the practice of moral self-cultivation which derive from the 3 ethical and spiritual traditions and together “offer us a shared frame of reference and a developmental scaffold for a technomoral virtue ethic of global scope” (Vallor, 2016: 64). The seven are: 1. Moral habituation; 2. Relational understanding; 3. Reflective Self-examination; 4. Intentional self-direction of moral development; 5. Perceptual attention to moral salience; 6. Prudential judgment; 7. Appropriate extension of moral concern.

Vallor discusses each element in some detail over several chapters. Then she develops a set of particular virtues she calls *technomoral virtues* because they are particularly relevant to the task of achieving the good life in common on a global scale in our highly technologically mediated age. And if she's right, the time to focus on their wide development among people worldwide is now. Again, Francis shares her urgent concern.

Let us take a closer look at what Vallor calls: *relational understanding*, *prudential judgment*, and *appropriate extension of moral concern*. Each of the core elements are important and reflects the Pope's concerns about the damage to humans and creation otherwise that is bound up with the rapid influx of digital technologies into so many lives. She sums up the process of relational understanding this way: 1. The habitual pursuit of an increasingly nuanced and holistic understanding of how one is bound to other members of one's moral community by friendship, kinship, shared human being and other salient ties (83); 2. A

lifelong effort to improve one's understanding of these relations and the moral concerns they generate, including fostering empathy, care, justice and civic friendship; and 3. The use of such understanding in prudential judgment called for by such relationships in particular circumstances (Vallor, 2016: 83).

She discusses the importance of the technomoral virtues and develops the ideas especially in her later focus on empathy, care, civility, and flexibility. Francis's concern for encounter resonates strongly here. Put briefly, if processes of encounter are necessary for relational understanding to develop, and if relational understanding is crucial for the proper development of empathy, care, civility and the employment of prudential judgment – then the sabotage of encounter by digital technology is of paramount importance. This is in part an empirical question. However, we likely need to take action now to avoid the dangers of digital technology and amplify its benefits, based upon (still) initial indicators, before all the relevant data are in.² And by the way, young people who have grown up swimming in the seas of digital technologies and social media platforms may well develop the best, most innovative responses to the damaging effects of such technologies. They have been deeply immersed in them, while we of the baby boom, me generation, or Generation X have not. However, if we can be of help, we must join the voices of those like Vallor and Francis and do some of the philosophical and theological work to contribute.

² Surely it would help to review much more of the relevant data, but that must wait for another occasion. A bracing account of data available to Facebook about the harmful effects Instagram has on young girls can be found in Wells, Horwitz, and Seetharaman (2021). The *Wall Street Journal* series “The Facebook Files” explores even more such revelations.

A second core element is *prudential judgment*. As she observes, this captures most of what Aristotle calls *phronesis*. *Phronesis* is often translated as “practical wisdom” which she calls “the exemplary virtue of the morally cultivated person” (Vallor, 2016: 105). Prudential judgment is one piece of this larger whole, a crucial one no doubt, but not the whole itself. Practical wisdom as a general capacity ready to apply in day-to-day decisions (big or small) rests upon the 5 core elements she discussed prior. These range from being habituated to moral acts to intentionally steering one’s life and character towards the good. Yet ethical actions would often not take place without proper discernment. She defines this prudential judgment as: “the cultivated ability to deliberate and choose well, in particular situations, among the most appropriate and effective means available for achieving a noble or good end” (Vallor, 2016: 105).

We see prudential judgment at work in people whom we admire as having good sense, who can take in a somewhat novel or chaotic situation and find a way to make good decisions within it. Very importantly, they are not bound by existing rules. Vallor observes “[t]hey are not overly distressed by unexpected or novel problems to which existing moral rules and conventions do not easily apply, nor do they fall victim to ‘analysis paralysis’ when those rules or conventions appear to conflict” (105). Those with prudential judgment are able to find the right balance in a variety of circumstances, especially in ones that challenge ordinary decision makers, keeping their sense of self-control and finding the right course of action. And if they have the other relevant virtues, they take that action and ask others to do so when relevant.

Teachers who have fixed deadlines for assigned work often face the challenge of when to be flexible. Maybe the rule is: no late work unless you are sick and have a doctor’s note or the like to prove that. But then there’s the case of an otherwise diligent student who got “food poisoning” the evening before a big assignment was due. They were up all-night vomiting and the

like but weren't able to visit a doctor to get proof. Sometimes you simply take the student's word and grant the extension. Some students offer too many variations on this theme in a given term and by the 3rd or 4th time, it becomes appropriate to hold them to the deadline. Prudential judgment concerns the conceptual processing part of coming to such a correct decision. If such deliberation discerns that several will work, but one must be decided in a timely fashion – then that is what such a person decides. They choose one and act.

This brings us to *appropriate extension of moral concern*. Regarding such extension, we can briefly note its key components. “A fully cultivated person with practical wisdom will be able to extend her moral concern appropriately—that is, to the right beings, at the right time, to the right degree, and in the right manner” (Vallor, 2016: 116). One of the big challenges with this occurs in the daily balancing act of honoring competing, significant demands on our moral concern. The emerging digital technologies challenge us because they present such new, dramatic, and unprecedented opportunities and pitfalls. Here there arises the obvious question of acute technosocial opacity. But even so, Vallor's gloss provides an appropriate aspirational goal even if we substitute “excellently” for fully, and “close to right” for “right”. This presupposes the proper integration of the other moral habits, especially moral attention and prudential judgment. It's the most demanding requirement. To do so reliably is arguably both necessary and sufficient for practical wisdom: “the cultivated state of the exemplary person with complete (though not *perfected*) virtue” (Vallor, 2016:117). When it comes to sorting out appropriate policies regarding digital technologies, from anti-trust law to privacy protection, one can't expect one with skill at this appropriate extension to get it all right. However, our chances of success depend upon working to cultivate such

virtue as much as possible among present and future decision-makers.

Vallor proceeds to outline her list of *techomoral virtues*, especially important being: empathy, care, civility, flexibility. They offer the closest set of complementary virtues to Francis' principles of dialogue, encounter, and kindness. Here are her basic glosses.

Empathy is “a cultivated openness to being morally moved to caring action by the emotions of other members of our technosocial world” (Vallor, 2016:133).

Care or *loving service to other* is “a skillful, attentive, responsible, and emotionally responsive disposition to personally meet the needs of those with whom we share our technosocial environment” (138). This is important as a bridge between Vallor's approach and that of Francis because it's here that she explicitly mentions love. Francis clearly makes love of neighbor a centerpiece of his moral vision. Arguably, the combination of empathy, care, and what follows, “civility” (with its noted synonyms: respect, tolerance, engagement, friendship) capture a suite of concerns animating much of the relational bonding needed according to Francis to navigate the moral challenges of digital technologies.

Civility is “a sincere disposition to live well with one's fellow citizens of a globally networked information society: to collectively and wisely deliberate about matters of local, national, and global policy and political action; to communicate, entertain, and defend our distinct conceptions of the good life; and to work cooperatively toward those goods of technomoral life that we seek and expect to share with others” (Vallor, 2016: 141).

This resonates well with what Francis means by social fraternity. The key to civility is a disposition to live well, involving a commitment to civil dialogue about how to pursue such, to face real and difficult differences, and to work through them as best one can for the benefit of everyone on earth, not simply a narrow

few; yes, a tall order. But one that she rightly observes, “the challenges of 21st century life demand” (Vallor, 2016:140).

Finally, there is **Flexibility**, which is “a reliable and skillful disposition to modulate action, belief, and feeling as called for by novel, unpredictable, frustrating, or unstable technosocial conditions” (Vallor, 2016: 145).

What would be the measure? She frames the correct moral standard around the common good over a reasonable length of time. Sometimes our moral rules are very good at discerning this, e.g. don’t steal, keep your promises. Other times, they need to be flexibly re-ordered. The grounding guideline for the classical traditions according to Vallor, has been a foundation in truth, i.e. reality rather than delusion.

Here we confront the boundary between classical and liberal notions of tolerance, and the ‘hard problem’ for cultivating a flexible public technomoral character. As we have noted, emerging technologies from global transportation networks to ICTs [information and communication technologies] increase our exposure to a plurality of conceptions of the good life, many of which are incommensurable with one another in part or in whole (Vallor, 2016: 146).

This challenge of moral and cultural incommensurability is not new and the classical Aristotelian, Confucian and Buddhist traditions reflected upon it. However, “[t]he truly novel challenge of our contemporary technosocial environment is the extent to which 21st century technology networks—the speed, range, and power of which have grown by many orders of magnitude in mere decades—ensure the radical and virtually irreversible interdependence of these morally incommensurable cultures and communities” (Vallor, 2016: 146-47). Live and let live will not quite do it.

So many people's fates all over the world depend upon what "humans *collectively* and *globally* practice" (Vallor, 2016: 147).

Still so many decisions are made that are grounded in parochial, local interests. If made by authoritarian regimes, then the challenge is for such leaders to exhibit the virtues (not impossible; for better or worse, that is the picture of Plato's *Republic*, a classic of the Greek virtue tradition). If made by democratically elected leaders, then the relevant will of the people in such places must take into serious consideration broader global interests (think globally, act locally – e.g. vote).

The virtue of technomoral flexibility calls for modulating actions when new circumstances call for it. Vallor observes, "[w]e now add that today, this entails something not seen as virtuous by classical traditions: an intelligent and habituated disposition to forbear those cultural value-systems and beliefs that do not significantly impair the ability of their possessor to cultivate and exercise practical wisdom in matters of global technosocial concern" (Vallor, 2016: 147). That is—how are decisions made within various cultures to engage in mutual tolerance in the interests of global civility and flourishing? On the other hand, she asks, "which norms cannot safely be tolerated because they are objectively inimical to such agency and thus to the flourishing of our species and planet" (Vallor, 2016: 148). She argues that local cultures of "feminine virtue" that conflict with the education or civic participation of women would be intolerable according to this criterion of how to apply flexibility. The main reason is that women play such a significant role in each culture to shape technosocial practices that their exclusion from deliberations aiming to guide prudently such practices "is globally self-defeating" (Vallor, 2016: 148).

Vallor sketches a wonderful short case study where she discusses the "Facebook Home" campaign and the notion we can avoid friction in our relationships. It plays a key part in her important chapter-long discussion of new social media and the technomoral virtues. I will not do it justice here, but she describes an

advertisement for Facebook Home depicting a teen at an awkward family dinner using Facebook to avoid having to listen to a lengthy and boring monologue by some elder relation. However, this allows her to avoid occasions of friction which are crucial for developing key virtues. “The moral world of adulthood in any culture is one in which relational bonds of family, friendship, work, and civic life require us to care for, understand, and engage deeply with people who we at least initially find to be boring, weird, irritating, alienating, or exasperating” (Vallor, 2016: 164). As we’ll see, this is exactly the sort of situation of friction in relationships that Francis has in mind by exhorting us to embrace encounter.

Encounter is easy when we’re around people we like, especially when they do things we enjoy, such as preparing a favorite meal for us, etc. It’s obviously more challenging when we’re in difficult, confrontational situations such as a public demonstration where counterdemonstrators shout obscenities at us or worse. Vallor argues that it’s in such situations of friction where the right amount of care and flexibility are crucial for a world to exist that we should want to live in. It’s part of being highly skilled at navigating difficult conversations that really need to take place.

A fuller examination would consider the key lessons from Vallor’s case studies in her chapter on social media. But suffice it to say, she shares much of the urgent concern that Francis expresses and her set of virtues are meant to frame a response, rather than suggest particular policy or behavioral solutions. Similarly, Francis emphasizes key virtues and spiritual processes not to offer a particular solution, but a framework for particular solutions and responses. Vallor’s relational understanding along with her addition of empathy, care, and civility capture much of the tenor of Francis’s emphasis on social fraternity grounded in love, coupled with

his emphasis on dialogue and encounter. However, unsurprisingly, the spiritual elements and single-minded focus on certain aspects of human dignity set the Pope's discussion apart. Vallor's virtues may falter or lack the urgency and sacrifice needed to transform lives in the face of the crucial structural difficulties of today's tech world. The ubiquity, embeddedness, economic, financial, and political power of the tech giants may require something quite deep for an adequate response. A spiritual transformation of the heart in the mode of Francis's framing seems necessary to avoid some significant wreckage. Vallor importantly models ways to frame, for a technological age, some of the Christian themes the Pope emphasizes.

3. Pope Francis on Encounter in the Digital Age.

The practices of *dialogue and encounter* are, for Francis, *the* key factors to engaging digital technology well. We might simplify his approach this way: to the degree that digital technologies can be designed, implemented, engaged, and otherwise used to foster dialogue and encounter – they will support the health of people and communities. But, to the degree that they sabotage dialogue and encounter, they will degrade and harm communities.

Approaching, speaking, listening, looking at, coming to know and understand one another, and to find common ground: all these things are summed up in the one word “dialogue”. If we want to encounter and help one another, we have to dialogue (FT 198).

Encounter and dialogue, when they occur, are the glue holding communities together. And when they are lacking, communities fail to thrive.

Because encounter and dialogue are bound together, two sides of the same coin, it's important to gloss what qualities good dialogue requires. Three issues at least, are of central concern. The first is simply for there *to be* real dialogue with others, especially with those who see things differently. Such conversation builds our skill in acknowledging each other's common humanity. Two,

good dialogue allows for the voices of the marginalized to be heard and expressed, which happens too infrequently. Third, it's the only hopeful process for humans to engage each other in a radically pluralistic global context – where the alternatives to dialogue are ongoing stalemates of tension or ultimately, violence. And we might understand *encounter* fundamentally to mean: engagement with others based in real dialogue.³

Authentic dialogue among people and communities clearly allows for the expression of views in ways authentic to those who hold them, as opposed to the manipulated caricatures so common in the short bursts of digital media channels. This can play a crucial role in allowing pluralism and diversity not only to exist without conflict but possibly to work together to solve mutual problems and illuminate deeper truths.

Based on their identity and experience, others have a contribution to make, and it is desirable that they

³ As others in this volume have commented, the philosopher Emmanuel Levinas has provided a profound account of what Francis seems to mean here by encounter. I do not mean to suggest that Levinas' and Francis's views are exactly the same, but simply that Francis echoes some central themes developed in depth by Levinas. For two careful and thoughtful explorations of the thought of Levinas in light of fundamental responsibilities to our neighbour, see Kunz (1998, especially ch. 6, 131 – 57) and Severson (2011). A tightly argued account of the conditions for knowing persons can be found in Benton (2017); he cites Lapidot-Lefler and Barak (2012) in arguing: "At the very least, personal encounters can have a positive impact on our moral behaviour toward those individuals: some empirical findings suggest that eye-contact characteristic of our third grade of personal involvement leads to more civil and moral behaviour toward those individuals, compared with merely knowing someone's name (knowledge-who typical of our first grade) or with seeing the person (characteristic of our second grade of personal involvement) (Benton, 2017, 828).

should articulate their positions for the sake of a more fruitful public debate. When individuals or groups are consistent in their thinking, defend their values and convictions, and develop their arguments, this surely benefits society. . . . Indeed, “in a true spirit of dialogue, we grow in our ability to grasp the significance of what others say and do, even if we cannot accept it as our own conviction. In this way, it becomes possible to be frank and open about our beliefs, while continuing to discuss, to seek points of contact, and above all, to work and struggle together” (FT 203).

With digital media, the danger of mis- and dis-information is heightened. Genuine dialogue can help address this in a way that supports common ethical concerns and projects.

Francis displays some hope in the potential of digital media to afford encounter and solidarity. He notes new possibilities that they offer. But for such possibilities to be realized, there must be appropriate guidance. Such guidance would encourage the media to afford encounter (i.e. be an amenable pathway; like having prominent well-designed, attractive or “irresistible” staircases in buildings affords the use of stairs (Bullitt Center 2022)). Vallor emphasizes such guidance as well. One approach to guidance is that we get the right rules and policies in place. Surely policies and rules have a role to play in certain contexts and with certain governments, e.g. the U.S. is arguably behind the curve (see the comments of Senators, e.g. Klobuchar and others in the Congressional hearing with Frances Haugen, the Facebook whistleblower, in October of 2021). Yet without a sufficient development of the virtues (which for Francis includes certain spiritual practices) the best policies can only help so much.

Francis realizes the tension between the positive promise and the risk, much of which we have seen play out in too many atrocious and tragic events (from the Jan. 6 insurrection in the US to the attacks on the Rohingya in Myanmar, to the use of digital media

for terrorist recruitment, and many more). He here outlines the basic vision of how the notion of encounter must guide digital media. “In today’s globalized world, ‘the media can help us to feel closer to one another, creating a sense of the unity of the human family which in turn can inspire solidarity and serious efforts to ensure a more dignified life for all The media can help us greatly in this, especially nowadays, when the networks of human communication have made unprecedented advances. The internet, in particular, offers immense possibilities for encounter and solidarity. This is something truly good, a gift from God’” (FT 205). Echoing the recent arguments of the Bishops of Australia, he insists that we must ensure modern forms of digital media and communication “are in fact guiding us to generous encounter with others, to honest pursuit of the whole truth, to service, to closeness to the underprivileged and to the promotion of the common good . . . we cannot accept ‘a digital world designed to exploit our weaknesses and bring out the worst in people’” (FT 205).

Here, Francis’ politics based on love and social solidarity feature centrally. While the character traits of global citizens in their use of digital media play an important role, the power of the tools cannot be ignored. An ongoing game of cat and mouse rages where the economics of the business models keep the pressure on for eye-balls and clicks. This promotes the design of sticky interfaces, platforms, and services. Digital media make money by understanding the psychology of the users at a whole new level of granularity. This has been fueled by unprecedented data and allows for increased sales (the Amazon model) or ever greater data coupled with lots of use. This allows for advertising revenue – a model

used by Facebook and Google.⁴ Amazon uses this data to “serve its customers” in hitherto unimagined ways and intensity. In the face of this landscape of digitally mediated manipulation, disinformation, obfuscation, distraction, and otherwise fantasy-peddling, the future heroes will be those who “can break with this unhealthy mindset and determine respectfully to promote truthfulness, aside from personal interest. God willing, such heroes are quietly emerging, even now, in the midst of our society” (FT 202).

Francis argues that real consensus must be grounded in truth and opposition to distortions of truth. He adds that such genuine consensus based in truth will reveal a solid, objective foundation for shared values. He expresses faith that dialogue and encounter are elements of the antidote to the worries of pluralistic, incommensurable values. Here he shares Vallor’s concerns and offers one set of practices to find a way through. Mutual inquiry and conversation may reveal a sufficiently robust set of values grounded in the truth of what’s necessary for the common good.

In a pluralistic society, dialogue is the best way to realize what ought always to be affirmed and respected apart from any ephemeral consensus. Such dialogue needs to be enriched and illumined by clear thinking, rational arguments, a variety of perspectives and the contribution of different fields of knowledge and points of view. Nor can it exclude the conviction that it is possible to arrive at certain fundamental truths always to be upheld. Acknowledging the existence of certain enduring values, however demanding it may be to discern them, makes for a robust and solid social ethics. (FT 211).

⁴ For a provocative, thoughtful, and harrowing account of how Google and Facebook have harnessed data for a new kind of surveillance capitalism, see Zuboff (2015).

Unsurprisingly, Francis opposes skepticism, relativism, and reductionism in the human ability to discern moral truth, pluralism notwithstanding. “The fact that certain rules are indispensable for the very life of society is a sign that they are good in and of themselves. There is no need, then, to oppose the interests of society, consensus and the reality of objective truth. These three realities can be harmonized whenever, through dialogue, people are unafraid to get to the heart of an issue” (FT 212).

Encounter is at the center of this project and allows especially for the marginalized to illuminate important values that otherwise would be missed if only the powerful had a hearing. The internet, social media, and like digital technologies promised a particularly powerful decentralization in the flow of information. At best it has been a mixed bag. In a suggestive gloss on encounter Francis offers the image of a society as a polyhedron.

Life, for all its confrontations, is the art of encounter. I have frequently called for the growth of a culture of encounter capable of transcending our differences and divisions. This means working to create a many-faceted polyhedron whose different sides form a variegated unity, in which “the whole is greater than the part”.[205] The image of a polyhedron can represent a society where differences coexist, complementing, enriching and reciprocally illuminating one another, even amid disagreements and reservations. Each of us can learn something from others. No one is useless and no one is expendable. This also means finding ways to include those on the peripheries of life. They have another way of looking at things; they see aspects of reality that are invisible to the centres of power where weighty decisions are made (FT 215).

A culture of encounter means a style of living where we “should be passionate about meeting others, seeking points of contact, building bridges, planning a project that includes everyone” (FT 216).

To harness digital technologies to foster encounter with the marginalized requires a commitment to many of the core elements Vallor outlines. Users must become accustomed to social friction and negotiating such challenges. That can happen face to face or digitally. But it must happen early and often in a way that mediates virtuous habits. Social peace requires craftsmanship. “What is important is to create processes of encounter, processes that build a people that can accept differences. Let us arm our children with the weapons of dialogue! Let us teach them to fight the good fight of the culture of encounter!” (FT 217).⁵ Francis shares Vallor’s concern with addressing pluralism and ethical incommensurability. His case for encounter and healthy dialogue rests in part upon their promise to address concerns about value pluralism and incommensurability – i.e. one cannot find sufficient common values to come to some sort of meaningful consensus with others. To this end he distinguishes mere tolerance from dialogic realism. “A false notion of tolerance has to give way to a dialogic realism on the part of men and women who remain faithful to their own principles while recognizing that others also have the right to do likewise” (FT 221).

Where can the Church play a key role in this process of dialogue and encounter? It can contribute at many levels from its own uses of digital technologies to guidance offered by leaders (such as Francis’s letter and that of the Australian Bishops), to what gets discussed in churches on Sunday from the pulpit. It should involve educational institutions from parochial schools to universities, convents, and seminaries playing a significant role.

⁵ One of the most powerful articulations of a practical model of this spirit is Loretta J. Ross’ TED talk on the culture of “calling-in” vs. calling-out (Ross, 2021).

Maybe they can pioneer some of the practices of encounter that the Francis has in mind. And hopefully they are open to learning from other communities when such have discerned processes of encounter that support the vision outlined.

And finally, Francis emphasizes the crucial importance of kindness, (he doesn't say "niceness"). Of course, one can be kind but still firm, especially in responding to injustice. This amounts to his own take on the important technomoral virtues of empathy, care and civility. He emphasizes the fundamental role of basic kindness and contrasts it with a consumerist individualism that in difficult times, e.g. COVID, leads to an every person for themselves mentality. "Yet even then, we can choose to cultivate kindness. Those who do so become stars shining in the midst of darkness" (FT 222).

Illuminatingly he grounds his invocation of kindness on the thought of St. Paul.

Saint Paul describes kindness as a fruit of the Holy Spirit (Gal 5:22). He uses the Greek word *chrestótes*, which describes an attitude that is gentle, pleasant and supportive, not rude or coarse. Individuals who possess this quality help make other people's lives more bearable, especially by sharing the weight of their problems, needs and fears. . . . It involves "speaking words of comfort, strength, consolation and encouragement" and not "words that demean, sadden, anger or show scorn" (FT 223).

Kindness is not a mere "superficial bourgeois virtue" but the crucial "engine oil" for facilitating healthy relationships, communities, and the pursuit of reconciliation. By itself, it won't succeed. Yet without it, communities fail to thrive. Sometimes it can appear to be mere superficial politeness or niceness. But kindness has a much deeper reality if

cultivated and practiced out of love rather than social obligation.

Kindness “frees us from the cruelty that at times infects human relationships” and from the anxiety and frantic activity that leaves others on the margins and adds to our indifference (FT 224). He notes that for various reasons people too often neglect basic social graces such as saying “thank you”, “excuse me”, and like gestures of polite discourse. “Yet every now and then, miraculously, a kind person appears and is willing to set everything else aside in order to show interest, to give the gift of a smile, to speak a word of encouragement, to listen amid general indifference. If we make a daily effort to do exactly this, we can create a healthy social atmosphere in which misunderstandings can be overcome and conflict forestalled” (FT 224). Genuine kindness not only makes things better, i.e. more enjoyable, less stressful, etc., but it can also be part of a transformation of human relationship. “Precisely because it entails esteem and respect for others, once kindness becomes a culture within society it transforms lifestyles, relationships and the ways ideas are discussed and compared. Kindness facilitates the quest for consensus; it opens new paths where hostility and conflict would burn all bridges” (FT 224).

Clearly Francis privileges the way physically present, face to face encounters can cultivate the tools of genuine kindness. Conversely, the impersonal, rapid, and ultimately “designed for commerce” modes of digital communication can degrade kindness. Admittedly, digital media properly designed and pursued can afford kindness as well. Yet, it may take constant work and vigilance to push the relevant players to make that a priority. Among important guiding principles, Francis offers a philosophy of technology grounded in the affordance of dialogue and encounter. Those processes may be crucial in establishing among people a critical mass of Vallor’s technomoral virtues of empathy, care, civility, and flexibility.

4. Concluding Thoughts

When I watched Frances Haugen testify in front of Congress in October of 2021 (I saw it on YouTube – ironies abound), I was struck by what appeared to be a strong bi-partisan consensus among both Democrat and Republican Senators. Any observer of recent US politics knows this is an exceedingly rare event. We see consensus as well between Francis, Shannon Vallor, and journalists such as Adrienne LeFrance. It's not simply that digital technologies threaten significant risks and downsides that are byproducts of the good things they offer. Rather, they pose structural barriers to civil discourse and the ability of communities around the world to address basic shared challenges. This dysfunction is a very serious challenge to the integrity of democratic institutions and peaceful conflict resolution – nearly everywhere.

Vallor offers a philosophical analysis for a principled response; Francis offers a moral theological and spiritual vision. Neither delves into the policy details in any depth. However, for the policies to succeed, some deeper character and spiritual transformations are needed. Institutions influenced by Francis's leadership can help lead the way. Philosophical and psychological education can add to these efforts. Together we may be able to get the tiger by the tail. We would thus achieve a genuinely kind, virtuous response to the excesses of Facebook, Google (Alphabet), Amazon, Apple and their kindred corporations and political allies. Our hope is that a way can be found where platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and the like can be a means for affording kindness. Such effort will require Loretta J. Ross' wisdom of calling the key players *in* rather than calling them *out* (Ross 2021). The challenge involves being kind to those involved while we call *on* them to aid the rest of us in addressing the real issues. How we negotiate these

challenges together may be absolutely decisive for what Vallor calls “a future worth wanting”.

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